

Exploring the Acceptance of User Experience on E-clearance: A Measure to Quality Web Portal

Janepol G. Ballard

School of Information and Communication Technology
Northwestern Mindanao State College of Science and Technology,
Labuyo, Tanguib City Philippines

Hidear Talirongan, Florence Jean B. Talirongan
Misamis University, Ozamiz City, Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

The rate of technological development is increasing exponentially. Technologies like artificial intelligence and automation are paving the way for future innovations in IT. These days we can connect our refrigerators and thermostats to the internet, and robots are getting smarter by the day. Everything from transportation and communication to healthcare and social interaction has been improved by technological advancements.

According to (What Is the Importance of Technology? | Simplilearn, 2022), the best thing is that it constantly develops, allowing for ever more complex additions. Instant messaging and video calling are two examples of how far we've come from the days of the telephone. Technology has helped in automating tasks, sending reminders, communicating effectively, paying bills with a press of a button, and shopping for everything from groceries to investing in valuable assets without ever leaving the house.

Information technology encompasses making new digital data and its storage, transport, and interchange. The information that technology encompasses is more than just computers and the like. In this information age technology has penetrated every facet of our existence. It has had a profound effect on culture and permeates our daily life (Advantages and Disadvantages of Information Technology - Javatpoint, n.d.).

It is now possible for people to get data and information more quickly, simply, and cheaply. Additionally, it quickens business deals and helps speed up production and management tasks. It helps people from all walks of life access the web in more exciting and creative ways.

User Experience (UX) design is defined as one of the processes for creating a system, website, or app that meets the needs of its intended audience with minimal effort and maximum satisfaction. In addition, users' experiences will be achieved by integrating design, psychology, research, technology, and business.

The User Experience describes how a person feels after interacting with a product, software, system, or service. Moreover, it is the overall impression that a person has after utilizing a company's digital offerings, such as a website or a mobile app. A user interface, usability, and user research are just a few of the numerous factors that go into creating products focusing on the user's experience.

Using the evaluation and comparing the user-friendliness of digital goods across time, designers can use data provided by UX metrics. It is on the objective's functions about the quality of items by revealing where enhancements are needed. An integral part of user-centered design is user experience testing. This is also known as usability testing. If the systems satisfy customers' expectations and deliver a satisfying experience to end users without the UX testing then we can consider this a successful user experience.

The current study evaluated the acceptance of user experience on the E-Clearance using the Quality Web Portal for Measuring UX. User experience and user interface used the ISO tool for evaluation: The Standard User Experience Questionnaire with five scales of range for the user's experience.

E-Clearance Portal is one of the ways to lessen the traffic and hassle for many graduating or non-graduating students. The portal was used for USTP Panaon Students and allowed them to access and be cleared from all the requirements easily.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Overview of the Research Portal

The material of most traditional courses can be provided online and learning results can be accomplished by employing equivalents to face-to-face pedagogical approaches. They launched a platform called the Research Portal to get around these restrictions. The Research Portal is organized logically and follows the typical research process, giving users access to resources and integrated capabilities such as study supervision, participant recruiting, data gathering, analysis, and storage. The seamless online research environment is on par with, and in some ways better than, traditional on-campus resources (Rodafinos, 2018).

B. State of User Experience

Several institutions are beginning to use the User Experience Design for Learning, which uses the Honeycomb architecture for online learning; an individualized strategy for online instruction that considers students' motivations, interests, and routines. The user experience is the sum total of the users' reactions to using the technology which is in line with what has been determined to be optimal for users to provide them with a satisfying experience (Troop, 2020). (Sharma & Tiwari, 2022). We may be on the cutting edge of technology, but that doesn't mean we can't ensure a pleasant and easy user experience. In today's high-tech, fast-paced environment, UI/UX designers are entrusted with a great deal of responsibility for the definition of user interface guidelines, procedures, color scheme, and design process when discussing how to use a piece of software best, the term "user experience" is often used. Ideas from user interface and user experience design are crucial to and in visualizing and conceptualizing design problems. One of the ways to improve online communication is to let others know when you're online, but this can lead to unwanted assumptions about your personal life. Users should use caution when presenting themselves online because of their biased understanding of OSIs (Cobb, 2020). Current OSI design patterns that rely on apps are giving way to more user-friendly architectures.

C. Acceptance of the User's Experience on E-Clearance

According to Ardo (2021), students can save time and energy by using an online clearance system, which allows them to skip the long lines that often form at the start of each semester. The online clearance system has the potential to provide straightforward information management for institutions because of its web-based, universal accessibility. Clearing students through an online system is more effective than traditional methods since it saves time and eliminates stress for everyone involved. The online clearance system is fully functional and has features such as an easy-to-use interface and trustworthy validation.

D. Web-Based Clearance System

Clearance services are also necessary for departing or graduating students, but they are woefully lacking on most academic websites. After displaying the system's usability satisfaction rate at the "Easy" level, it demonstrates that users found the system as easy to use as they had hoped. In addition, it was agreed that the devised technique was straightforward or efficient and preferred to the current stringent method of carrying out graduate clearing services (Oliha, 2020).

According to Adamu (2022), every year, numerous educational institutions argue about the number of graduating students who must go through a process known as clearance. In the conventional clearance process, a student would visit various clearance offices, such as the student affairs office, the library, and most importantly, the registry department, to be endorsed for clearance. Too much time is wasted since the graduating student must physically go to other locations where important personnel may not be present and where data may be

duplicated or lost. Therefore, the clearance procedure can be simplified and made more convenient for both the student and the institution by using an online clearance system. The vast majority of students feel that the system has met or exceeded their expectations for usability, convenience of service delivery, and accessibility in terms of delivering effective and efficient clearance in a timely manner.

E. Usability Scale and Testing

According to Derisma (2020), numerous websites offer access to technological resources, including various forms of educational programming. Therefore, the usability of a system or website is crucial for its users to feel at ease when employing it, to gain the necessary knowledge, and to be interested in continuing to rely on the site throughout the learning process. The website's usability was rated at 72.1 on a scale from 0 to 100 by seasoned users and 70% by first-time visitors. In conclusion, the website for teaching computer programming can be used as a learning medium.

In addition, the new student acceptance system is one of the systems that may automate the admissions process, beginning with registration and continuing through the selection process and the announcement of the results of online elections. It conducts usability testing to measure how well something works and how happy its users are with it. Performance metrics reveal that the acceptance system works well for a sizable percentage of the population and that users are happy with the results after implementing the system (Uska et al., 2020).

F. Website Accessibility

Using data from the Sauer, Sonderegger, & Schmutz (2018) article, the technological device types may influence non-disabled users of all ages and types. Still, the website's accessibility is the most important aspect of all. Recent studies have shown that this has a good impact on the system's implementation for nondisabled users; however, it is yet unknown whether or not these benefits would extend to users of different ages or with other types of devices. Therefore, the findings revealed that for non-disabled users, task completion rate, task completion duration, and satisfaction ratings were all improved with enhanced accessibility. However, there was no association between user age and the increased speed with which tasks could be completed thanks to the tablet's convenient portability. This is an advantage that non-disabled people can enjoy thanks to accessible websites. It's an added bonus that its accessible design helps people of all ages who aren't disabled utilize it.

Based on the article of (Onay Durdu & Altuntas, 2020), websites have become a key information transmission vehicle for a wide range of organizations, both in the private and public sectors. According to the findings, software developers ensure that all users are considered when defining what constitutes an accessible website. User-centered techniques, which prioritize the needs of the website's visitors, are essential for making the

site accessible. As a result, laws should consider the ease of access to the internet.

Furthermore, the COVID-19 website developed and maintained by the Human Health Aspects in Public Health Agency during the epidemic, shows that accessibility violations have been spotted in accordance with accessibility principles, most of which happened when trying to adhere to desirability and operability principles. Some went to unusual lengths to make their sites more accessible, while others didn't put forth much effort, and the range was rather wide. (Murphy et al., 2022). And it seems like such efforts were on just doing the bare minimum. The accessibility of websites is not always obvious.

G. Web-Portal

The Open Community website is an excellent hub for platforms used solely for the dissemination of information and the distribution of expertise. Today, there is a burgeoning interest in technology whose sole purpose is to boost such platforms' technological prowess and quality. However, one of the issues with such systems is that it can be difficult to please everyone who uses them. This is especially true regarding usability and the quality of the user experience. The open community portal, Smart Ports Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Development, was used to build and test user scenarios. Finally, the portal interface was met with positive user comments and perspectives (Shabnam, 2022). This research is part of a larger effort to make the system more user-friendly and welcoming.

(Oliha, 2021). The effects of the coronavirus epidemic have highlighted the significance of an institution's web portal for alternate learning outside of traditional classrooms or lecture halls. With respect to learnability and the usability scale criteria for the online portal system has been regarded as one of the most effective. The research, however, demonstrates that the social, academic web portal platform in a pandemic period is flexible, usable, and can help promote social, and academic interactions between professors and students in educational institutions.

There needs to be an immediate focus on developing novel immunotherapy approaches and reliable indicators of response and resistance. These areas have benefited from developing bulk and single-cell gene expression profiling technologies, providing useful new data. However, there is a lack of rigorous examination and poor sorting of these materials, making their precise location impossible to ascertain. The data and user feedback can be analyzed with the help of some helpful modules. Patient immunotherapy and bioinformatics monitoring are made easier by this portal, which is designed specifically for use by medical facilities (Chen, 2022).

Web portals are increasingly being used by schools as a centralized location for managing student and staff data. The portal is an information system because it relied on data. How happy students are with a Web portal depends on some distinct aspects, including how good the material is, how good the

service is, how good the system is, and how valuable they find it. These same criteria also determine college students' satisfaction with utilizing the Internet for academic purposes. Whether or not a user returns to the portal depends on them as individuals (Adeyemi, 2020).

Individuals' levels of behavioral intention to use technology can be used as a predictor of their actual use of technology. Results show a favorable relationship between user reports of ease of use and behavioral intent to use and attitude toward usage. In addition, having a favorable outlook on use is closely linked to a greater propensity to take the intended action. Perceived usefulness, however, is unrelated to either behavioral intent to use or attitude toward use. Accordingly, the research has immediate and far-reaching consequences (Aditia, 2018).

One way this information might be shared is through a website's academic information system, as suggested by Augustina (2022). It's used by teachers and kids alike. However, users often need assistance understanding how to maximize the tool's capabilities. This makes individuals wait longer for responses to their inquiries and for their comments to be posted. User feedback was collected to determine the level of usability. According to the results, fourteen of the studied traits were determined to be very usable, while ten were found to be only somewhat so. Each criterion has a maximum and minimum score. However, the foundation of UI design is its characteristic. The most significant problem is the constant lag in new content updates.

According to (Abdulellah, 2022), the students, faculty, and the institution were all able to greatly benefit from the internship portal's implementation. The SIP is a web-based, user-friendly instrument for assessing training, administration, and advice. Students develop their skills with actual work experience after finishing an internship program. Students learn to apply what they've learned in the classroom to real-world situations in the medical field, all while maintaining their competency and professionalism. They also develop their professional skills in accordance with the requirements of the position and seek advice from others with more expertise in the field.

The literature of Adwan et al. (2021) suggests that the field of information systems is as dynamic and varied as the information technologies it employs in its pursuit of helping businesses achieve their long-term goals and ever-changing operational objectives. Recent graduates seeking employment and hiring organizations face difficulties. It's challenging for both job seekers and employers to discover positions that are a good match for their skills and expertise. Based on feedback from job seekers and businesses, we were able to pinpoint the shortcomings of existing commercial online job portals and the underlying causes of these problems.

III. METHODOLOGY

This chapter is about the collection stage of the study's research. Based on figure 1 starts with the distribution of a questionnaire to the students on the USTP Panaon campus. The users will test and evaluate the survey after using the portal for

clearing ratings. After gathering the data, the researcher used the UEQ tool, a Google form that lets the researcher enter the data and generate findings automatically, providing guidelines for data interpretation.

Fig. 1: Research Framework of the Study

A. Questionnaire Development

There are two key components in the questionnaire: User Profile and UEQ for Web-Portal in Clearance. The User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) comprises all six scales and twenty-six items. As a result, it gauges attractiveness, efficiency, perspicuity, dependability, stimulation, and

innovation of the products—in this case, the E-Clearance—which are all important factors. Table 1 lists the variables (which are scales) and research items that were taken from the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) as a whole. Figure 2 shows standard UEQ.

Table 1: The following are the variables used in the study

The variables or Scales	Definition	Items
Attractiveness	The attractiveness is how the system attracts students. Regarding the use of E-Clearance Portal.	1. annoying - enjoyable 2. good - bad 3. unlikable - pleasing 4. unpleasant - pleasant 5. attractive - unattractive 6. friendly - unfriendly
Efficiency	It will measure the effectiveness of user experience when using the Portal.	1. fast - slow 2. inefficient - efficient 3. impractical - practical 4. organized - cluttered
Perspiciuity	It is a guideline used to learn and understand the uses of the website.	1. not understandable - understandable 2. easy to learn - difficult to learn 3. complicated – easy 4. clear - confusing
Dependability	It is a user experience scale that measures the expectations of the users on the system.	1. unpredictable - predictable 2. obstructive - supportive 3. secure - not secure 4. meets expectations - does not meet expectations
Stimulation	It measures the valuable level of the system. If it is interesting or not to use as a school E-Clearance Portal.	1. valuable - inferior 2. boring - exciting 3. not interesting – interesting 4. motivating - demotivating
Novelty	The E-Clearance Portal depends on the creativity and conservation of the system.	1. creative - dull 2. inventive - conventional 3. usual - leading edge 4. conservative - innovative

The scales' three goal-oriented or pragmatic qualities are perspicuity, efficiency, and reliability. On the other side, novelty and stimulation are two excellent perspectives that are not goal-oriented. While attractiveness is the fact or condition of being common, users' responses to the attractiveness scale

are generated by their responses to the responses for the other scales. The items on the questionnaire are arranged as a semantic differential, with each entry comprising a few words having the opposite context.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
annoying	<input type="radio"/>	enjoyable	1						
not understandable	<input type="radio"/>	understandable	2						
creative	<input type="radio"/>	dull	3						
easy to learn	<input type="radio"/>	difficult to learn	4						
valuable	<input type="radio"/>	inferior	5						
boring	<input type="radio"/>	exciting	6						
not interesting	<input type="radio"/>	interesting	7						
unpredictable	<input type="radio"/>	predictable	8						
fast	<input type="radio"/>	slow	9						
inventive	<input type="radio"/>	conventional	10						
obstructive	<input type="radio"/>	supportive	11						
good	<input type="radio"/>	bad	12						
complicated	<input type="radio"/>	easy	13						
unlikable	<input type="radio"/>	pleasing	14						
usual	<input type="radio"/>	leading edge	15						
unpleasant	<input type="radio"/>	pleasant	16						
secure	<input type="radio"/>	not secure	17						
motivating	<input type="radio"/>	demotivating	18						
meets expectations	<input type="radio"/>	does not meet expectations	19						
inefficient	<input type="radio"/>	efficient	20						
clear	<input type="radio"/>	confusing	21						
impractical	<input type="radio"/>	practical	22						
organized	<input type="radio"/>	cluttered	23						
attractive	<input type="radio"/>	unattractive	24						
friendly	<input type="radio"/>	unfriendly	25						
conservative	<input type="radio"/>	innovative	26						

Fig. 2: The standard User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ)

B. Sample Selection

The profile of the respondents is shown in Table 2. The researchers selected 225 students from the University of Science and Technology of Southern Philippines (USTP) Panaon who are students or participants. The respondents already used the E-Clearance Portal (ECP). The responders are specifically enrolled in any of the institution’s undergraduate programs. The researchers chose a representative sample of 500 students, from which they collected data from nearly 225 students.

Slovin’s formula is calculated as

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$$

where:

- n = sample size
- N = population size
- e = acceptable margin of error

C. Data Collection, Validity, and Reliability

The students were provided access to an online survey that asks them to fill out their profiles and score their overall satisfaction with the web services. The respondents were given a brief orientation on completing the standard questionnaire since the items were placed in pairs of terms with opposite meanings to help them develop correct and reliable responses. Numerous studies that examined the validity and reliability of the standard UEQ scales revealed that the scales had a high level of dependability.

Table 2: Participants of the study

Respondents	Description	Frequency
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology	These are students enrolled in an IT Course.	81
Bachelor of Science Technology Livelihood Education Major in Home Economics	Students taking their degree generally in education, and home economics.	109
Bachelor of Science in Marine Biology	These are the students taking Marine-related courses.	35

D. Data Analysis

The scale for the UEQ goods ranges from -1 to +5. Consequently, the most unfavourable reaction is -1, and the most favorable response is +5. Positive user feedback is indicated by a number over +5, while negative feedback is shown by a number below -1. The observed scales' means have a typical range of -2 to +4. When a scale's mean is close to +4, the respondents gave positive feedback.

Calculating the means of the six scales served as the foundation for UEQ analysis. Since factor analysis was used to design it, it does not consider the calculation of the overall mean of all scales because this figure cannot be interpreted. This excludes the entire score for the UX. Additionally, a scale's mean value between 2.0 and 3.8 indicates a high-quality perspective for that scale.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter will see the tables, findings, analysis, and interpretation of the data on the study. This chapter has nine tables overall together with the discussion for every table.

Table 3: Age of the Participants

Respondents	Frequency
15-20 years old	85
21-25 years old	105
26-30 years old	27
31-35 years old	8
36 years old and above	0
Total	225

Table 3 shows that the majority of students' ages are between 21 and 25 years old. The responders are therefore in their early years of adulthood, according to the data. No responders were enrolled in the 36 and older age category, the oldest age group. The researchers selected 225 students to evaluate and test the system.

Table 4: Sex of the Participants

Respondents	Frequency
Male	68
Female	155
Prefers not to say	2

Table 4 shows the sex of the participants, who can be either male or female or would like not specify their sex. According to the data, 155 total female students tested the E-Clearance Portal, 68 total male students, and 2 total students who prefer not to state their sex.

Table 5: Attractiveness Scales

Attractiveness Scales						
Items	1	2	3	4	5	Mean
Enjoyable-Annoying	1	3	51	86	84	4.11
Good-Bad	1	0	42	104	78	4.15
Pleasing-Unlikeable	10	5	91	75	44	3.62
Pleasant-Unpleasant	1	2	65	90	67	3.97
Attractive-Unattractive	3	4	46	87	85	4.09
Friendly-Unfriendly	0	2	36	69	118	4.35

Table 5 shows the attractiveness ratings of the E-Clearance Portal. The researchers evaluated the E-Clearance Portal's attraction to users or USTP Panaon students using this scale. The attractiveness factor had a mean score of 4.09. At the same time, the system's user-friendliness had a mean score of 4.35 in total. In addition, the system has a mean score of 1.79

unpleasant and is strongly disagreed by most students. However, the system got a mean score of 1.83, which shows that students strongly disagree with it, yet they do not all agree that it is unattractive. And while the overall mean for positive variables is 4.05, or agreed, the overall mean for the negative scales is 1.79, or strongly disagree.

Table 6: Perspicuity Scales

Perspicuity Scales						
Items	1	2	3	4	5	Mean
Understandable-Not understandable	3	2	30	80	110	4.29
Easy to learn-Difficult to learn	1	1	36	79	108	4.29
Easy-Complicated	1	4	41	82	97	4.2
Clear-Confusing	5	2	55	83	80	4.03

Table 6 is about the perspicuity level of the E-Clearance Portal. On this scale, the researchers determined if the system E-Clearance Portal is clear to users or USTP panaon students. The mean score for the clearness factor was 4.03. The mean score for the user's ability to quickly learn how to use the system is 4.29. The system also has a 4.2 mean score and most users feel it is simple. The system got a 2.03 mean score, which

indicates that students did not all agree with the statement that it is complicated. The students also disagree with the system's confusion factor, which has a mean score of 2.16. Also, the overall mean for negative scales is 1.95, which is considered disagreeable, while the overall mean for positive scales is 4.21, which is considered to be strongly agreed.

Table 7: Efficiency Scales

Efficiency Scales						
Items	1	2	3	4	5	Mean
Fast-Slow	4	3	52	86	80	4.04
Efficient-Inefficient	2	1	60	101	61	3.97
Practical-Impractical	2	2	63	80	78	4.02
Organized-Cluttered	0	2	31	80	112	4.34

Table 7 shows the E-Clearance Portal's efficiency. The researchers evaluated the system's E-Clearance Portal's effectiveness for users or USTP Panaon students using this scale. With a mean score of 3.97, the effective factor. A total of 4.04 is the typical speed at which the system can be used by a user. The system also has a 4.34 mean score, is well-organized, and most people strongly agreed. But despite getting a mean score of 1.98, which indicates that students disagree, they do not all agree that the system is inefficient. Next, given the fact that the system's slowness has a mean score of 2.06, the students also disagree with it. The overall mean for negative scales is

2.07, considered to disagree, while the overall mean for positive scales is 4.09, considered to be agreed.

Table 8: Dependability Scales

Dependability Scales						
Items	1	2	3	4	5	Mean
Predictable-Unpredictable	1	2	69	95	58	3.92
Supportive-Obstructive	1	1	53	98	72	4.06
Secure-Not secure	1	2	40	81	101	4.24
Meet expectations-Doesn't meet expectations	1	4	60	64	96	4.11

Table 8 shows the E-Clearance Portal's dependability. This scale was used by the researchers to evaluate the dependability of the E-Clearance Portal to Users or USTP Students. The mean score for the unpredictable factor was 1.99. While the system has provided users with a mean score of 4.11, expectations have been met. Additionally, the system is secure and most users strongly agree; its mean score is 4.24. However, while getting a mean score of 1.85, which indicates that

students strongly disagree with it, students do not entirely agree that the system is unsafe. The fact that it does not satisfy the system's expectations—in fact, it has a mean score of 1.94—is something else that the students disagree with. The overall mean for negative aspects is 2.12, considered to disagree, while the overall mean for positive factors is 4.08, considered to be agreed.

Table 9: Stimulation Scales

Stimulation Scales						
Items	1	2	3	4	5	Mean
Valuable-Inferior	2	1	42	85	95	4.2
Exciting-Boring	2	3	70	78	72	3.95
Interesting-Not interesting	1	0	50	86	88	4.15
Motivating-Demotivating	2	2	56	95	70	4.02

Table 9 shows the E-Clearance Portal's Stimulation scale. The researchers used this scale to evaluate how motivating the E-Clearance Portal is for users or USTP Panaon students. The motivating element got a total score of 4.02, indicating that most students agreed that the system's development was motivating. While the user has a total of 3.95 means was also or strongly agree as a verbal interpretation, the excitement of using the system. Additionally, the system is interesting and

most users agree, with a mean score of 4.15 or agree. Although the system got a 1.83 mean score, which indicates that students disagree with it, the students do not entirely agree that it is not interesting. The student's high response to the system's demotivational factor—which has a mean average of 1.99—followed by this. And although the overall mean for positive variables is 4.08, or agree, the overall mean for negative scales is 2.12, or disagree.

Table 10: Novelty Scales

Novelty Scales						
Items	1	2	3	4	5	Mean
Creative-Dull	4	3	43	90	85	4.11
Inventive-Conventional	14	15	110	45	41	3.37
Usual-Leading Edge	8	20	108	53	36	3.39
Innovative-Conservative	0	3	60	90	72	4.03

Table 10 shows the E-Clearance Portal's novelty scale. The researchers used this scale to determine if USTP Panaon students or users are being provided using the system's E-Clearance Portal. A mean of 3.21 was calculated for the leading edge factor. While the system's originality was realized in how the user used the system, with a mean score of 4.11 overall. Additionally, the system is motivating and most users agree as shown by its 3.37 mean score. However, while getting a mean score of 2.01, which indicates that students disagree, students

do not entirely agree that the system is dull. The average student score on the system, which has a mean of 3.39, is also neutral. Additionally, the overall mean of the negative scales is 2.87, considered moderate, while the overall mean of the positive variables is 3.73, also considered moderate.

Table 11: Six Means of UEQ Scales for E-Clearance Portal

Scale / Variable	Mean
Attractiveness	4.05
Perspiciuity	4.21
Efficiency	4.09
Dependability	4.08
Stimulation	4.08
Novelty	3.73
Total Mean	4.04

Table 11 displays the means for the six criteria used to evaluate the E-Clearance Portal website based on the UEQ tool and the information from the 225 respondents. The results show that attractiveness has a mean score of 4.05, efficiency at 4.09 and a high interpretation, perspicuity at 4.21, dependability at 4.08, and stimulation at 4.08 with a high interpretation. The novelty has a high mean score of 3.73 on the Likert scale. Additionally, the E-Clearance Portal's overall user experience rating is 4.04, indicating that students have a positive opinion of the system's usability.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter discusses the summary, discussions, conclusions, and implications of the findings and recommendations based on the findings. The purpose of this study is to determine the acceptance of users on the E-Clearance Portal. This chapter summarizes findings, conclusions, and recommendations drawn from the findings in relation to the E-Clearance Portal.

A. Summary of the Findings

The prime importance was the studies' findings per the study's objectives. A summary of the findings is presented below.

Overall the respondents enjoyed using the E-Clearance Portal. The attractiveness mean of the study is interpreted as neutral. The respondents agree that the system is easy to use, learn and understand. Moreover, based on the response of the students most of them also agree that it is clear to use. Also, the students agreed that the system is organized, practical, and efficient. That their requirements will be accessible and easier for them to view. The students are secure and meet the expectations of the E-Clearance Portal based on the functionality and features. Besides, it is one of the websites that are interesting to use according to the evaluation of students. With the six user experiences of scale or variable, it shows that it is neutral. And lastly, most of the students are in the Bachelor of Science Technology Livelihood Education Major in Home Economics track and are female.

B. Conclusion

This study investigated the following:

Most respondents are female and Bachelor of Science Technology Livelihood Education Major in Home Economics students. The E-Clearance Portal acceptance used the UEQ tool to measure the attractiveness, perspicuity, dependability, novelty, efficiency, and stimulation scale. Out of 225 respondents, 87 of the students agree on its attractiveness, while 83 students agree that E-Clearance Portal is clear. In addition 101 of the participants also agree on the efficient experience of the portal and 78 of them agree on the stimulation or excitement of using the system.

C. Recommendations

- The researchers highly recommend that future researchers may incorporate other research methods like interviewing which can help with purposive sampling.
- The researchers recommend that the programmer try to use other languages for developing E-Clearance Portal.
- The researchers recommend that the School Admin implement the E-Clearance Portal to make the students and their work easier and more convenient.
- The researchers also recommend future developers should use mobile applications for school clearance.

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